

**CONCEPT AND TYPES OF FORMS OF CRIME PREVENTION.
CONCEPTS, CONTENT AND APPLICATION OF WRITTEN, ORAL AND
VISUAL FORMS OF CRIME PREVENTION.**

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Annotation. After gaining independence, our country began to form its independent position in the fight against crime. In this regard, it is recognized that it is better to prevent crimes than to expose the culprits, punish them, compensate for the damages caused to the victims, and ensure the execution of punishments, and comprehensive reforms in the judicial and legal sphere have been implemented. Crime prevention has become a priority in our country's fight against crime. This was also reflected in the newly adopted laws, amendments and additions to the laws during the years of independence.

Keywords: crime, types of crime, prevention, oral, written and visual prevention.

Any activity has its own forms and methods in order to achieve its goal and effectively ensure the performance of assigned tasks. Similarly, crime prevention activities have their own forms and methods. However, it can be observed that until recently, in legal sciences, the theoretical basis of the forms and methods of crime prevention activities, that is, their content, the basis of their application, procedure and conditions, have not been revealed in detail. Both in theory and in practice, when talking about the prevention of violations, in particular, crimes, the main attention was paid to the types of prevention and the system of measures. Later, forms and methods existing in other areas of law were gradually applied to the field of crime prevention. Paragraph 4 of the "Regulation on the base point of internal affairs bodies" approved by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 18, 2017 No. 1281-uz" as one of the main requirements for persons appointed to the positions of prevention inspectors, as well as in Chapter 2 of the "Regulation on the General Directorate of Crime Prevention of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan" "the practice of applying legislation, law, as well as forms and methods of crime prevention development of proposals for improvement" as one of the main tasks of the General Directorate made the importance of this issue even more urgent. Later, forms and methods existing in other areas of law were gradually applied to the field of crime prevention. In this

regard, in order to ensure the implementation of this task, the following functions have been performed by the main administration:

a) to ensure the introduction of modern criminalistic techniques, information and communication technologies, criminalistic and fast-databases for the prevention of crimes, to make suggestions on improving the methods of crime prevention;

b) preparation of information-analytical materials, reviews and recommendations on issues of improvement of crime prevention activities;

c) study, generalize and spread the positive experience that is effectively used in the activities of internal affairs bodies, including in the field of crime prevention in foreign countries;

d) to develop effective forms and methods and uniform principles of work for the organization of crime prevention in cooperation with higher education, scientific-research institutions and other organizations.

e) It should be emphasized that each form of crime prevention has its own characteristics. Z.S. Zaripov and M.YU. In their research, Kerjner considered crime prevention from the point of view of two forms of activity, consisting of "preventive" and "law enforcement". In some literature, the four forms of crime prevention, i.e. written, oral, visual and electronic, are mentioned, but their content is not explained.

f) In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, "shape" is explained by the words "appearance, image, style, method". If we give a more precise explanation to the concept of "shape", 1) the external appearance, surface appearance, expression of the thing; 2) a certain appearance, a thing in a mold, a figure; 3) the condition and appearance of the body; 4) expressive side of the content, appearance, expression; 5) it becomes clear that it means a way, a method of doing something. So, a conclusion is formed that the form is the external appearance of the content of a certain event or action, and it can also be the form of the method. That is why H.R. Alimov, A.A. Makhmudov, N.T. Ismailov state

g) said that the method of persuasion in management is different and includes several forms. In philosophical literature, the form represented the appearance. For example, forms of movement of material existence are distinguished into: mechanical, physical, chemical, biological and social movements. Kh.Kh., who spoke about management forms. Bakhramov believes that "in understanding the essence of these forms, special attention should be paid to concepts such as "management purpose", "management functions",

"management tasks", "authority", "competence". As can be seen from the above, the form of prevention of offenses is the external appearance of the content of activity and behavior in the prevention of offenses. In elucidating the nature of the form of prevention, it is necessary to rely on the purpose, function and tasks of crime prevention. Most criminological literature mentions forms of crime prevention, but their content is not clarified.

Verbal, written, and visual forms of legal propaganda among the population on crime prevention have been shown. In some textbooks, these forms are presented not only as a form of legal promotion, but also as a form of crime prevention. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account the purpose, functions, tasks, specific features and advantages of prevention, as well as the reforms in this field and the development of information and communication technologies when forming a system of crime prevention forms. Based on the scientific opinions of legal scholars and the results of the analysis of the practice of prevention of offenses, the forms of prevention of offenses are recorded in the following system:

- writing; oral; demonstrative; electron; mixture; control; guarding; rescue; marked; SMS (MMS) message.

The written form of crime prevention differs from other forms of prevention by its purpose, function and application. The goal of prevention in written form is to have a preventive effect on the population (one or several persons) by conveying information about the prevention of offenses through specific language and word combinations written in the alphabet, as well as legal regulation of relations in the field of prevention of offenses.

The following is a written form of prevention of violations tasks are:

- preventive effect on the basis of written information;
- providing information with preventive content in a simple, fluent language that is understandable to everyone;
- formation of understanding, knowledge and skills in individuals through information with preventive content presented in writing;
- warning persons in writing about the inevitability of punishment for a guilty illegal act (action or inaction);
- to require persons to perform or not to perform certain actions in writing (official warning), etc. The written form of crime prevention, according to its content, usually in newspapers and magazines, the causes and conditions of crimes, methods and means of committing crimes, articles about criminals,

stories about committed crimes, short stories, essays, crowded It is manifested by posting written notices in the places where there will be violations, sending letters aimed at informing citizens about the causes and conditions of the detected violation, the inevitability of the punishment for the violation, as well as the factors of suffering from the violation.

In this regard, procedural documents such as laws and statutory documents on the prevention of violations, written submissions on the causes of violations and the conditions that allow them to be committed, and official warnings are among them. The written form of crime prevention provides the following opportunities:

- implementation of laws, statutory documents, assignments, instructions, preventive programs and plans with binding force for all in social life;
- causing legal consequences as a result of not following written procedures for performing or not performing certain actions;
- quick and accurate reception of information;
- delivery of large amounts of information to individuals;
- using information for a long time without remembering it, etc.

When applying the written form of crime prevention the following are prohibited:

- providing false and unfounded information;
- make spelling mistakes;
- use of words that can be interpreted in different meanings;
- writing preventive information in a language, dialect and jargon that the population does not understand, etc.

The written form of crime prevention is widely used in crime prevention, and it also appears in the mixed form of prevention. We will discuss this in detail below. Therefore, the written form of crime prevention is to deliver information about crime prevention to individuals in writing (through the law, legal documents, written materials of the mass media, posters, bulletin boards, written posters, etc.), to carry out work related to crime prevention. is a form of preventive activity aimed at the like. The oral form of crime prevention is mainly lectures, interviews, question-and-answer sessions, broadcast of audio-recorded announcements and warning calls, radio appearances, and loudspeakers around streets, public places, and apartment buildings. it is manifested in preventive measures such as giving lons. In this regard, audio books, audio messages distributed on Internet social networks, and audio lessons are among them. Each of the oral preventive measures has its own characteristics, and their

implementation requires a responsible approach. During the implementation of each preventive measure, steps such as preparation, direct implementation, analysis of results, elimination of existing problems and shortcomings should be followed in sequence. For example, a lecture is usually done in relation to a group of individuals. For this, at the stage of preparation for the lecture, which problematic issue (causes and conditions of the crime, method and means of committing it, social danger of the crime and the criminals, what categories of people are mainly affected, reasons for the injury, etc.) will be clarified, the members of the lecture audience (listeners) will be thoroughly studied and information about their gender, age, education, profession, needs and interests will be collected. Also, the audience capacity, equipment, and technical capabilities of the audience will be studied, and on this basis, what methods and tools will be used during the lecture will be determined in advance. At the stage of direct delivery of the lecture, first of all, it is necessary to arouse motivation, i.e. interest of the audience to listen to the lecture.

After that, it is considered appropriate to refer the information, evidence and facts related to the lecture in a logical sequence to the judgment of the audience. During the lecture, the audience, that is, the listeners, should be under constant control, they should not be bored, and live communication should be established as much as possible. During the lecture, as well as at the end, the speaker should answer the questions of the audience as fully as possible, and if there is not enough time to answer, he should take the questions with him, and in the process of preparing for future lectures, he should make presentations within the framework of these questions. It is recommended to get rich. In order to prevent the loss and theft of things and the disappearance of young children in the markets and other shopping centers, railway stations and airports, and to increase the vigilance of the population in the subways, organize the broadcasting of audio recordings that call on the citizens to be constantly aware. It also gives good results.

The goal of verbal prevention is to have a preventive effect on the population (one or several persons) by verbally conveying information about crime prevention in a specific language. The following are the tasks of the oral form of crime prevention:

- preventive effect based on oral information;
- oral presentation of information with preventive content in understandable, simple, fluent words in a language understood by persons affected by preventive measures;

- calling people to awareness and vigilance through information with preventive content presented orally;
- verbally warning individuals about the inevitability of punishment for a guilty illegal act (act or inaction);
- verbally requiring individuals to perform or not perform certain actions, etc., according to the grounds established by law.

The oral form of crime prevention provides the following opportunities:

- attracting the attention of the population;
- providing the latest information, in particular, prompt notification of the danger, incident;
- conducting quick questions and answers in lectures, conversations, interviews, etc., obtaining additional information;
- providing information to individuals quickly and concisely.

When using the oral form of crime prevention the following are prohibited:

- providing false and unfounded information;
- Lakhcha, use of various "parasite" words;
- expressing thoughts without understanding;
- disclosure of personal and state secrets.

Verbal form of prevention of offenses is also used in giving verbal orders, instructions and recommendations for effective organization and coordination of prevention of offenses. This form of prevention can also appear in a mixed form. So, the oral form of crime prevention is lecturing to people (directly, online or in the form of audio recording), talking, conveying information and messages about crime prevention through mass media, is a form of preventive activity aimed at providing instructions, tasks and recommendations on the organization and coordination of crime prevention.

Demonstration form of crime prevention, like written and oral forms, can be implemented separately or in a mixed form. Some written sources also incorporate elements of visual form. Among our people, the proverb "It is better to see once than to hear a thousand times" reveals the importance and necessity of the visual form of crime prevention. The effectiveness of the visual form is that the information is based on real reality, the events that happened or may happen are described, and the given information is explained through pictures, fragments, and slides. In this regard, the demonstration of exhibition stands, video clips, fragments, movies and cartoons, TV shows, performances, etc. will give good results. Most of the preventive measures carried out in a

demonstrative form are filmed and shown on the basis of a pre-prepared script. The vitality of the scenario and the clear goal orientation ensure the impact of the visual material. For example, the effectiveness of a video showing the tragic consequences of criminal acts such as corruption, terrorism, religious extremism, drug addiction, and human trafficking depends on the viability of the script and the skill of the creative team.

In addition, by placing pictures of a transport vehicle that has been damaged by a terrible traffic accident, and when you see it, you suspect that a living person has come out of it, or a similar vehicle on a certain stand, with a child crying because of the loss of loved ones. - placement on the edge of the carriageway is sure to alert any driver who passes by this road. Preventive measures carried out in the form of a demonstration depend not only on the content of the demonstration material, but also on what time, in what place, and in what audience it will be broadcasted, placed, and shown. Usually, videos with preventive content are recommended to be shown during the airing of serials and shows that people love to watch.

- Depending on the issue and who needs to be more preventively affected, the exhibition stands will be hung on the streets, avenues, on the side of the road of vehicles, markets, supermarkets, metro stations, railway stations and airports. gives a positive effect. The purpose of visual prevention is to have a preventive effect on the population (one or several persons) by showing video clips, fragments, movies and cartoons, TV shows, plays, hanging exhibition stands, placing models.

- The following are the tasks of the demonstrative form of crime prevention:

- preventive effect through visual means;
- through information with preventive content presented on the basis of the demonstration of visual aids, to call people to awareness and vigilance, to provide knowledge on the prevention of offenses;
- describe the events that have occurred or may occur (such as theft, invasion, fraud, robbery, corrupt situations, traffic accidents), as well as commenting on the given information through pictures, fragments, slides;
- creating an image in the minds of the population about the negative socio-legal consequences of anti-social behavior such as jealousy, invisibility, greed, drug addiction, drunkenness, prostitution, etc.

When using the demonstrative form of crime prevention, the following is required:

compliance of the content of the exhibition materials with the requirements of the state policy, law and regulatory documents related to the prevention of offenses;

- to have the conclusion of a specialist (lawyer, psychologist, etc.) on the presentation of visual materials to the general public;
- preparation of demonstration materials based on pedagogical and psychological rules;
- giving a brief explanation or conclusions to the visual materials that are more difficult to grasp at a glance.

Therefore, the demonstrative form of crime prevention is the preparation and broadcast of programs, films, videos about crimes on television, hanging posters and announcements with the content of crime prevention in crowded places, showing videos, meetings, lectures. It is a form of preventive activity aimed at the use of multimedia tools, stage performances, etc.

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